

Deliverable D.4.1.1
Survey on (publicly)
accessible (meta-)data for
Risk Assessment
Workpackage WP4

Responsible Partner: ANSES

Contributing partners: RIVM

GENERAL INFORMATION

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Dissemination <i>Author's suggestion to inform the following possible interested parties.</i>	<p>OHEJP WP 1 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 2 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 3 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 4 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 5 <input type="checkbox"/> OHEJP WP 6 <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>OHEJP WP 7 <input type="checkbox"/> Project Management Team <input checked="" type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Communication Team <input type="checkbox"/> Scientific Steering Board <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>National Stakeholders/Program Owners Committee <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>EFSA <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> ECDC <input type="checkbox"/></p> <p>Other international stakeholder(s):</p> <p>Social Media:</p> <p>Other recipient(s):</p>

SURVEY ON (PUBLICLY) ACCESSIBLE (META-)DATA FOR RISK ASSESSMENT

The deliverable is accessible at the following address:
https://survey.anses.fr/SurveyServer/s/formation7/questionnaire_RA/questionnaire.htm

The zip file created with the software Sphinx (used for realizing the questionnaire) is also available : D.4.1.zip

The questions (in black) and modalities (in blue) can also be found below

ab

1.

Q6_Title_of_the_study

Title of the study

Mandatory response.

2.

Q7_Obj

What were the objectives of your study?

Evaluation of illness risk

Process assessment

Evaluation of illness; Risk following outbreak; Exposure assessment; Health burden assessment; Interventions (assessment impact of performant objective, microbiological criteria, ...); Process assessment; Risk ranking; Assessment impact of performant objective and microbiological criteria; Interventions; Other

Mandatory response. An "If Other, please specify" question is associated with this question. You can check more than one box.

ab

4.

Q8_country

Which country was included?

Mandatory response.

5.

Q9_hazard

Hazard(s): define as precisely as possible: e.g. STEC O157, *Campylobacter spec.*, *Campylobacter jejuni*, *Salmonella Typhimurium*

Modalité 1; Modalité 2; *Aeromonas caviae*; *Aeromonas hydrophila*; *Aeromonas spp.*, unspecified; *Aeromonas veronii*; Aichi virus; *Anisakis*; *Anisakis simplex*; *Anisakis spp.*, unspecified; Astrovirus; Avastrovirus; *Bacillus*; *Bacillus anthracis*; *Bacillus cereus*; *Bacillus cereus* toxins; *Balantidium*; *Balantidium coli*; *Balantidium spp.*, unspecified; Biogenic amines; Bovine enterovirus; *Brucella*; *Brucella - B. abortus*; *Brucella - B. canis*; *Brucella - B. ceti*; *Brucella - B. melitensis*; *Brucella - B. noetomae*; *Brucella - B. ovis*; *Brucella - B. pinnipedialis*; *Brucella - B. suis*; *Brucella spp.*, unspecified; Calicivirus; *Campylobacter*; *Campylobacter - C. pylori*; *Campylobacter coli*; *Campylobacter cryaerophilus*; *Campylobacter curvus*; *Campylobacter fetus*; *Campylobacter fetus* subsp. *fetus*; *Campylobacter fetus* subsp. *venerealis*; *Campylobacter gracilis*; *Campylobacter hominis*; *Campylobacter hyointestinalis*; *Campylobacter hyointestinalis* subsp. *hyointestinalis*; *Campylobacter hyointestinalis* subsp. *lawsonii*; *Campylobacter jejuni*; *Campylobacter jejuni* subsp. *doylei*; *Campylobacter jejuni* subsp. *jejuni*; *Campylobacter lari*; *Campylobacter mucosalis*; *Campylobacter pylori* subsp. *mustelae*; *Campylobacter rectus*; *Campylobacter spp.*, unspecified; *Campylobacter sputorum*; *Campylobacter sputorum* subsp. *bubulus*; *Campylobacter sputorum* subsp. *mucosalis*; *Campylobacter sputorum* subsp. *sputorum*; *Campylobacter upsaliensis*; Cestodes; *Clostridium*; *Clostridium - C. botulinum*; *Clostridium - C. difficile*; *Clostridium perfringens*; *Clostridium spp.*, unspecified; *Coxiella*; *Coxiella burnetii*; *Coxiella popilliae*; *Coxiella spp.*, unspecified; *Cronobacter*; *Cronobacter sakazakii*; *Cronobacter spp.*, unspecified; *Cryptosporidium*; *Cryptosporidium parvum*; *Cryptosporidium spp.*, unspecified; *Cyclospora*; *Cyclospora cayetanensis*; *Cyclospora spp.*, unspecified; *Cysticerci*; *Cysticerci of Taenia saginata*; *Cysticerci of Taenia solium*; *Cysticerci spp.*, unspecified; *Diphyllobothrium*; *Diphyllobothrium latum*; Duvenhage virus; *Echinococcus*; *Echinococcus granulosis*; *Echinococcus multilocularis*; *Echinococcus oligarthrus*; *Echinococcus spp.*, unspecified; *Enterococcus*; *Enterococcus spp.*, unspecified; *Enterococcus faecalis*; *Enterococcus faecium*; *Enterococcus*, pathogenic; *Enterococcus*, pathogenic - *E. faecalis*; *Enterococcus*, pathogenic - *E. faecium*; *Enterococcus*, pathogenic - *Enterococcus spp.*, unspecified; Enteroinvasive *E. coli* (EIEC); Enteropathogenic *E. coli* (EPEC); Enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC); Enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC); Enterovirus; *Erysipelothrix*; *Erysipelothrix rhusiopathiae*; *Erysipelothrix spp.*, unspecified; *Escherichia coli*; *Escherichia coli* VTEC, unspecified; *Escherichia coli* VTEC, unspecified1; *Escherichia coli*, non-pathogenic; *Escherichia coli*, non-pathogenic, unspecified; *Escherichia coli*, pathogenic; *Escherichia coli*, pathogenic1; *Escherichia coli*, pathogenic - Verotoxigenic *E. coli* (VTEC) - VTEC O75:H5; *Escherichia coli*, pathogenic, unspecified; *Escherichia coli*, pathogenic, VTEC; *Flavivirus*; *Flavivirus dengue* virus; *Flavivirus Japanese encephalitis* virus; *Flavivirus Kyasanur forest disease* virus; *Flavivirus Langat* virus; *Flavivirus Louping ill* virus; *Flavivirus Omsk haemorrhagic fever* virus; *Flavivirus Powassan* virus; *Flavivirus St. Louis encephalitis* virus; *Flavivirus tick borne encephalitis* virus (Eastern); *Flavivirus tick borne encephalitis* virus (Greek goat); *Flavivirus tick borne encephalitis* virus (Turkish sheep); *Flavivirus tick borne encephalitis* virus (Western); *Flavivirus West Nile* virus; *Flavivirus yellow fever* virus; *Flavivirus*, unspecified; Foodborne viruses; *Francisella*; *Francisella philomiragia*; *Francisella spp.*, unspecified; *Francisella tularensis*; Fungi; *Giardia*; *Giardia intestinalis* (lamblia); *Giardia spp.*, unspecified; *Hantavirus*; *Hepatitis A* virus; *Hepatitis E* virus; *Hepatitis virus*; Histamine; *Leptospira*; *Leptospira borgpetersenii*; *Leptospira interrogans*; *Leptospira interrogans* serovar *Icterohaemorrhagiae*; *Leptospira interrogans* serovar *Saxkoebing*; *Leptospira interrogans* serovar *Sejroe*; *Leptospira kirschneriae*; *Leptospira spp.*, unspecified; *Listeria*; *Listeria - L. grayi*; *Listeria ivanovii*; *Listeria monocytogenes*; *Listeria seeligeri*; *Listeria spp.*, unspecified; *Listeria welshimeri*; *Mamastrovirus*; *Microsporium*; *Microsporium canis*; *Mycobacterium*; *Mycobacterium - M. avium* complex; *Mycobacterium - M. avium* complex - *M. avium* subsp. *avium*; *Mycobacterium - M. avium* complex - *M. avium* subsp. *hominissuis*; *Mycobacterium - M. bovis*; *Mycobacterium - M. microti*; *Mycobacterium - M. pinnipedii*; *Mycobacterium africanum*; *Mycobacterium avium*; *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *avium*; *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *paratuberculosis*; *Mycobacterium avium* subsp. *silvaticum*; *Mycobacterium caprae*; *Mycobacterium celatum*; *Mycobacterium fortuitum*; *Mycobacterium intracellulare*; *Mycobacterium kansasii*; *Mycobacterium scrofulaceum*; *Mycobacterium spp.*, unspecified; *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*; *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* complex; *Mycobacterium xenopi*; *Mycobacterium*, atypical; *Nairovirus*; *Nairovirus Crimean Congo haemorrhagic fever* virus; *Nairovirus spp.*, unidentified; Nematodes; *Neorickettsia*; *Neorickettsia risticii*; norovirus (Norwalk-like virus); Parasites; *Plesiomonas*; *Plesiomonas shigelloides*; *Plesiomonas spp.*, unspecified; Protozoa; *Rotavirus*; *Rotavirus1*; *Salmonella*; *Salmonella - Not typeable*; *Salmonella - Other serovars*; *Salmonella - S. Typhimurium*, monophasic; *Salmonella Dublin*; *Salmonella enterica*, monophasic; *Salmonella Enteritidis*; *Salmonella Typhi*; *Salmonella Typhimurium*; *Salmonella Virchow*; *sapovirus* (Sapparo-like virus); *Sarcocystis*; *Sarcocystis hominis*; *Sarcocystis spp.*, unspecified; *Sarcocystis sui*hominis; *Shigella*; *Shigella boydii*; *Shigella dysenteriae*; *Shigella flexneri*; *Shigella sonnei*; *Shigella spp.*, unspecified; *Staphylococcal enterotoxins*; *Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin A*; *Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin B*; *Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin C*; *Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin D*; *Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin E*; *Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin H*; *Staphylococcal enterotoxins - Enterotoxin*, unspecified; *Staphylococcus*; *Staphylococcus - S. aureus*; *Staphylococcus - S. aureus*, methicillin

resistant (MRSA); Staphylococcus - S. pseudintermedius, meticillin resistant (MRSP); Staphylococcus enterotoxins; Staphylococcus intermedius; Staphylococcus spp., unspecified; Staphylococcus suis; Staphylococcus zoonoticus; Streptococcus; Streptococcus spp., unspecified; Strongyloide spp., unspecified; Strongyloides; Strongyloides stercoralis; Thermophilic Campylobacter spp., unspecified; Tick-borne encephalitis virus (TBE); toxigenic V. cholerae; toxigenic V. parahaemolyticus; Toxocara; Toxocara canis; Toxocara spp., unspecified; Toxoplasma; Toxoplasma gondii; Toxoplasma spp., unspecified; Trichinella; Trichinella britovi; Trichinella nativa; Trichinella pseudospiralis; Trichinella spiralis; Trichinella spp., unspecified; Trichinella T6; Trichophyton; Trichophyton mentagrophytes; Trichophyton spp., unspecified; Trichophyton verrucosum; Unspecified Lyssavirus; Unspecified Microsporium; Vesiculovirus; Vesiculovirus Chandipura virus; Vesiculovirus spp., unidentified; Vesiculovirus Vesicular stomatitis virus; Vibrio; Vibrio - V. cholerae; Vibrio - V. parahaemolyticus; Vibrio spp., unspecified; Vibrio vulnificus; Viruses; Yersinia; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 1A; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 1B; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 1B-O:13; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 1B-O:21; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 1B-O:7; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 1B-O:8; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 2; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 2-O:5,27; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 2-O:9; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 3; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 3-O:3; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 3-O:5,27; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 4; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 4-O:3; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 5; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 5-O:1,2,3; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 5-O:2,3; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - biotype 5-O:3; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - O:1,2,3; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - O:13; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - O:21; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - O:7; Yersinia - Y. enterocolitica - O:8; Yersinia enterocolitica; Yersinia enterocolitica non typable; Yersinia enterocolitica O:1; Yersinia enterocolitica O:2,3; Yersinia enterocolitica O:3; Yersinia enterocolitica O:5; Yersinia enterocolitica O:5,27; Yersinia enterocolitica O:6; Yersinia enterocolitica O:9; Yersinia enterocolitica unspecified; Yersinia frederiksenii; Yersinia intermedia; Yersinia kristensenii; Yersinia molaretti; Yersinia pseudotuberculosis; Yersinia spp., unspecified; Other1

Mandatory response. Une question "Si Autre, précisez" est associée à cette question. Cochez au maximum 10 cases.

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7.

Q10_product

Product: define as precisely as possible, including the animal species in case of meat. Ground pork meat, ground beef meat, filet américain, salad, red fruits, ... (See Tab 9.Products)

Alcoholic beverages1; Amphibians and Reptiles1; Animal fats and oils (processed fat from animal tissue)1; Animal other organs (edible offals non-muscle)1; Barbecue or steak sauces1; Berries and small fruits, PROCESS=Freezing1; Berries and small fruits, PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Bovine muscle; Bovine, minced meat, USE=Intended to be eaten cooked, PROCESS=Freezing 1; Bovine, minced meat, USE=Intended to be eaten cooked, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Bovine, minced meat, USE=Intended to be eaten raw, PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Bovine, minced meat, USE=Intended to be eaten raw, PROCESS=Freezing1; Bread and similar products1; Brined cheese (feta-type and similar)1; Bulb vegetables, PROCESS=Freezing1; Bulb vegetables, PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Butter; Buttermilk, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Buttermilk, PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation)1; Canned anchovies1; Canned herring1; Canned mackerel1; Canned salmon1; Canned sardines1; Canned seafood1; Canned sprats1; Canned tunas and similar1; Canned-tinned meat1; Cereal doughs -based products; Cereal grains and similar and primary derivatives thereof; Chicken fresh meat; Chicken fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing1; Chicken fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Citrus fruits, PROCESS=Freezing1; Citrus fruits, PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Cods, hakes, haddocks; Cods, hakes, haddocks, PROCESS=Freezing1; Cods, hakes, haddocks, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Composite dishes; Compote of fruit / vegetables1; Confectionery including chocolate1; Conserve (Composite dishes, PROCESS=Statistical sterilisation (in batch or package), PROCESS=Canning / jarring)1; Continental european brown cooked sauce, gravy1; Cooked cured or seasoned bovine meat1; Cooked cured or seasoned pork meat1; Cooked cured or seasoned poultry meat1; Cooked sausages1; Cow milk, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Cow milk,PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation)1; Cow milk,PROCESS=UHT; Crabs, sea-spiders; Crabs, sea-spiders, PROCESS=Freezing1; Crabs, sea-spiders, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Cream and cream products, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Cream and cream products, PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation)1; Cured pork fat (ex lardon)1; Cured ripened raw sausages1; Cured seasoned bovine meat1; Cured seasoned pork meat1; Cured unripened raw sausages1; Dairy fats1; Dairy imitates1; Deer fresh meat; Deer fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing1; Deer fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Dessert sauces/toppings1; Diadromous fish; Diadromous fish, PROCESS=Freezing1; Diadromous fish,PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Dried fish1; Dried seafood1; drinking water; Duck fresh meat; Duck fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Eggs and egg products; Equine muscle; Equine muscle, PROCESS=Freezing1; Equine muscle, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Extra hard cheese (parmesan, grana type), PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Sheep for milk production1; Extra hard cheese (parmesan, grana type), PROCESS=Raw,

no heat treatment, SOURCE=Dairy cows1; Extracts of plant origin1; Fat emulsions and blended fats; Fine bakery wares1; Firm/semi-hard cheese (gouda and edam type), PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Sheep for milk production1; Firm/semi-hard cheese (gouda and edam type), PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Dairy cows1; Firm/semi-hard cheese (gouda and edam type), PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Goat for milk production1; Firm/semi-hard cheese (gouda and edam type), PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Sheep for milk production1; Firm/semi-hard cheese (gouda and edam type), PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Dairy cows1; Firm/semi-hard cheese (gouda and edam type), PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Goat for milk production1; Firm-ripened bloomy (white mould) or washed rind cheese, PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Goat for milk production1; Firm-ripened bloomy (white mould) or washed rind cheese, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Sheep for milk production1; Firm-ripened blue mould-veined cheese, PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Dairy cows1; Firm-ripened blue mould-veined cheese, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Goat for milk production1; Firm-ripened cheese with added herbs, spices or other ingredients1; Fish meat and products thereof; Flounders, halibuts, soles1; Flounders, halibuts, soles2; Flounders, halibuts, soles, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Flowering brassica, PROCESS=Freezing1; Flowering brassica,PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Foie gras1; Food for particular diets1; Food products for young population; Fresh raw sausages, SOURCE=Bovinae (bovines) 1; Fresh raw sausages, SOURCE=Generic poultry 1; Fresh raw sausages, SOURCE=Pig1; Fresh uncured cheese1; Freshwater crustaceans; Freshwater crustaceans, PROCESS=Freezing 1; Freshwater crustaceans, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Freshwater fish; Freshwater fish, PROCESS=Freezing1; Freshwater fish, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars, PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation)1; Fruit / vegetable juices and nectars,PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment; Fruit / vegetable spreads and similar; Fruit and primary derivatives thereof; Fruit or fruit-vegetable puree1; Fruit preparations for fillings and/or flavouring1; Fruit/vegetable juice concentrate 1; Fruit/vegetable juice powder1; Fruit/vegetables/plant drinks, spreads and related products; Fruiting vegetables, PROCESS=Freezing1; Fruiting vegetables, PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Fungi, PROCESS=Freezing1; Fungi, PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Game birds fresh meat1; Garden vegetables and primary derivatives thereof; Goat milk, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Goat milk, PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation)1; Goat milk, PROCESS=UHT; Goat muscle; Goat muscle, PROCESS=Freezing 1; Goat muscle, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Goose fresh meat; Goose fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Goose liver1; Guinea-fowl fresh meat; Guinea-fowl fresh meatPROCESS=Freezing1; Guinea-fowl fresh meatPROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Hard cheese (cheddar, emmental type), PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Sheep for milk production1; Hard cheese (cheddar, emmental type), PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Dairy cows1; Hard cheese (cheddar, emmental type), PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Goat for milk production1; Hard cheese (cheddar, emmental type), PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Sheep for milk production1; Hard cheese (cheddar, emmental type), PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Dairy cows1; Hard cheese (cheddar, emmental type), PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Goat for milk production1; Hen eggs1; Herbs, spices and similar1; Herbs/spices sauces1; Herrings, sardines, anchovies; Herrings, sardines, anchovies, PROCESS=Freezing1; Herrings, sardines, anchovies, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Honey1; Infant and follow-on formulae1; Ingredients for hot drinks and infusions1; Insects and arachnids (including species only consumed outside EU)1; Isolated purified ingredients (including mineral or synthetic); Jam, apricots1; Jam, blackberries1; Jam, blueberries1; Jam, cranberries1; Jam, currants (black)1; Jam, currants (red)1; Jam, gooseberries1; Jam, lingonberry1; Jam, mandarins1; Jam, mixed fruit1; Jam, oranges1; Jam, peaches1; Jam, plums1; Jam, raspberries1; Jam, rose hips1; Jam, sour cherry1; Jam, strawberries1; Jam, sweet cherry1; Juice, apple, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, apricot, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, beetroot, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, black currant, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, blackberry, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, carrot, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, celery, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, citrus, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, cranberry, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, cucumber, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, elderberry, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, grape, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, grapefruit, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, guava, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, lemon, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, lime, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, mango, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, nectarine, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, orange, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, passion fruit, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, peach, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, pear, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, pineapple, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, pomegranate, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, potato, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, prune, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, red currant, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, tomato, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, turnip, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Juice, white cabbage, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Lamb fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing 1; Lamb fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Leafy vegetables, PROCESS=Freezing1; Leafy

vegetables, PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Legume seeds and primary derivatives thereof; Legumes with pod, PROCESS=Freezing1; Legumes with pod, PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Liquid or gel separated from plant RPCs1; Liver-type sausage1; Lobsters, spiny-rock lobster; Lobsters, spiny-rock lobster, PROCESS=Freezing1; Lobsters, spiny-rock lobster, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Mammals and birds meat and products thereof; Mammals kidney1; Mammals liver1; Margarines and similar; Marinated / pickled fish1; Marinated / pickled seafood1; Marinated meat1; Marine fishes not identified; Marine fishes not identified, PROCESS=Freezing1; Marine fishes not identified, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Marmalade1; Mayonnaise, hollandaise and related sauces1; Meat and dairy imitates; Meat imitates1; Meat specialties1; Milk and dairy concentrate; Milk and dairy powders1; Milk and milk products (dairy); Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes; Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes, PROCESS=Freezing1; Miscellaneous coastal marine fishes, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Miscellaneous demersal marine fishes, PROCESS=Freezing1; Miscellaneous demersal marine fishes, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Miscellaneous fruits (generic), PROCESS=Freezing1; Miscellaneous fruits (generic), PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Miscellaneous pelagic marine fishes; Miscellaneous pelagic marine fishes, PROCESS=Freezing1; Miscellaneous pelagic marine fishes, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Mixed fruit and vegetable juices, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Mixed fruit juice, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Mixed fruit nectars, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Mixed juices with added ingredients, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Mixed vegetable juice, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Molluscs, SOURCE=Bivalvia - Clams, etc. (generic) 1; Mustard and related sauces1; Nectar, apple, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Nectar, apricot, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Nectar, banana, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Nectar, mango, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Nectar, orange, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Nectar, peach, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Nectar, pear, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Nectar, pineapple, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Nuts and primary derivatives thereof1; Oilseeds and oilfruits1; Ovine milk, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment1; Ovine milk, PROCESS=Thermal treatment (heating for preservation)1; Ovine milk, PROCESS=UHT; Partridge fresh meat; Partridge fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing1; Partridge fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Pasta and similar products1; Pastas and rice (or other cereal) – based dishes1; Pheasant fresh meat; Pheasant fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing1; Pheasant fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Pig muscle; Pig muscle, PROCESS=Freezing 1; Pig muscle, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Pigeon fresh meat; Pigeon fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing1; Pigeon fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Plants where the vegetative tissue is used as food, PROCESS=Freezing1; Plants where the vegetative tissue is used as food, PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Pome fruits, PROCESS=Freezing1; Pome fruits, PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Poultry kidney1; Poultry liver; Processed cereal-based food for infants and young children1; Processed or preserved fruits1; Processed or preserved vegetables and similar1; Quail fresh meat; Quail fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing1; Quail fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Rabbit fresh meat; Rabbit fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing1; Rabbit fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Ratites fresh meat; Ratites fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing1; Ratites fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Ready-to-eat meal for infants and young children1; Root and tuber vegetables (excluding starchy- and sugar-), PROCESS=Freezing1; Root and tuber vegetables (excluding starchy- and sugar-), PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Salad dressing1; Salads1; Salt1; Salted seafood1; Salt-preserved fish1; Sandwich and sandwich-like dishes1; Sauces from fermented/hydrolysed sources and similar1; Savoury extracts and sauce ingredients1; Sea urchins and other echinoderms1; Seafood and products thereof; Seasoning mixes1; Seasoning, sauces and condiments; Sharks, rays, chimaeras; Sharks, rays, chimaeras, PROCESS=Freezing1; Sharks, rays, chimaeras, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Sheep (adult) fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Sheep (adult) fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing 1; Sheep muscle; Shrimps and prawns; Shrimps and prawns, PROCESS=Freezing1; Shrimps and prawns, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Smoked fish1; Smoked seafood1; Snails 1; Soft - ripened cheese, =Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Goat for milk production1; Soft - ripened cheese, =Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Sheep for milk production1; Soft - ripened cheese, =Thermal treatment (heating for preservation), SOURCE=Dairy cows1; Soft - ripened cheese, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Goat for milk production1; Soft - ripened cheese, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Dairy cows1; Soft - ripened cheese, PROCESS=Raw, no heat treatment, SOURCE=Sheep for milk production1; Soups (dry mixture uncooked); Soups (ready-to-eat); Spoonable desserts and ice creams2; Spoonable desserts and ice creams3; Sprouts, shoots and similar, PROCESS=Freezing1; Sprouts, shoots and similar, PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Squids, cuttlefishes, octopuses1; Starchy roots and tubers1; Stems/stalks eaten as vegetables, PROCESS=Freezing1; Stems/stalks eaten as vegetables, PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Stone fruits, PROCESS=Freezing1; Stone fruits, PROCESS=Unprocessed1; Structured/textured fish meat products or fish paste1; Sugars (mono- and di-saccharides)1; Syrups (molasses and other syrups)1; Terrestrial animals other than mammals and birds; Tomato ketchup and related sauces1; Tomato-containing cooking sauces1; Tunas, bonitos, billfishes; Tunas, bonitos, billfishes, PROCESS=Freezing1; Tunas, bonitos, billfishes, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Turkey fresh meat; Turkey fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Vegetable fats and oils, edible1; Vegetables-based cooked sauce1; Vinegar1; White sauces1; Wild boar fresh meat; Wild boar fresh meat, PROCESS=Freezing 1; Wild boar fresh meat, PROCESS=Unprocessed 1; Other

Une question "Si Autre, précisez" est associée à cette question. Cochez au maximum 10 cases.

ab

9.

Q1_nameOrga

Name of Institut / Agency / Organization

Mandatory response.

ab

10.

Q2_namePers

First name and Last name of the scientist

Mandatory response.

c1

11.

Q3_email

Email adress

Mandatory response.

ab

12.

Q4_position

Position

Mandatory response.

13.

Q5_date

Date of questionnaire filling

"jj/mm/aaaa".

ab

14.

Q11_pop

Target population

15.

Q12_start

Indicate the starting point of model: e.g. farm phase, slaughter house, crop collection

Primary production (farm); Modalité 2; Distribution; Consumer stage (storage and preparation); Slaughterhouse; Primary production; Raising; Other

An "If Other, please specify" question is associated with this question. You can check more than one box.

[17-26].

Q13a_step_mp

Which step(s) along the food chain were included? For each step which microbiological processes are modelled?

Primary production; Processing; Distribution; Consumer stage (storage and preparation); Other; Primary production; Processing; Distribution; Consumer stage (storage and preparation); Other

[27-38].

Q14a_step_fh

Which step(s) along the food chain were included? For each step which food handling processes are modelled? (Choose from: partitioning, mixing, cross-contamination, removal)

Primary production; Slaughterhouse; Processing; Distribution; Consumer stage (storage and preparation); Other; Primary production; Slaughterhouse; Processing; Distribution; Consumer stage (storage and preparation); Other

Modalité 1; Modalité 2; Partioning; Removal; Cross-contamination

39.

Q15_final_point

Indicate the final point of model: e.g. end of production, consumer stage, ..

Modalité 1; Modalité 2; Consumer stage (storage and preparation); Slaughterhouse; Raising; Other

Une question "Si Autre, précisez" est associée à cette question.

ab

41.

Q17b_uncert

Did you perform an evaluation such as a sensitivity or uncertainty analysis?

ab

42.

Q18b_uncert

Did you perform an evaluation such as a sensitivity or uncertainty analysis?

ab

43.

Q13b_mp_other

If 'other', can you precise ?

44.

Q16c_DRDorS

Did you use a deterministic or stochastic model?

Modalité 1; Modalité 2; Other

Une question "Si Autre, précisez" est associée à cette question.

46.

Q18_software

Which software was used?

Modalité 1; Modalité 2; MicroHibro; R; @Risk; FSSP; FSK-Lab; Matlab; Risk ranger; Swift QMRA; FDA-iRisk;

Other1

An "If Other, please specify" question is associated with this question. You can check more than one box.

ab

48.

Q19_output

What kind of output? be specific and give the dimension of the output: e.g. no. of cfu ingested per person per year, no. of cases per 100,000 persons per year

ab

49.

Q20b_pub

Publication reference of the QMRA (e.g. Permanent link to a website, doi, article)

ab

50.

Q21_mrsc

Did you indicate the main route or source of contamination?

ab

51.

Q22b_reco

Did you recommend an intervention strategy?

52.

Q23_decision

Nature of the decision taken by risk manager using QMRA?

[Modalité 1](#); [Modalité 2](#); [Technical instruction](#); [Communication plan](#); [Other](#)

An "If Other, please specify" question is associated with this question. You can check more than one box.

ab

54.

Q24b_rdec

Publication reference of the riks manager decision?

55.

Q24a_Publication_reference

Question 24a: Publication reference of the riks manager decision?

[Modalité 1](#); [Modalité 2](#)

ab

56.

Q25b_datap

Did you use any data produced by yourself?

ab

57.

Q26b_DatalitW

Question 26b: If 'yes', which one?

ab

58.

Q27b_DataSNW

Did you use data from a scientific network (please indicate) ?

ab

59.

Q28a_HI

For hazard identification? (eg. data from outbreak investigations, data related to number of sporadic cases, characteristics of microorganisms throughout the food chain)

ab

60.

Q28b_HC

For hazard characterisation? (e.g. used parameters in dose-response model)

ab

61.

Q28c_EA

For exposure assessment? microbiological data (e.g. surveillance plan, industry own check results, contamination data (prevalence and concentration), parameters for microbiological and food handling processes: growth (curves), inactivation, cross-contamination, etc.)

ab

62.

Q28d_EAc

For exposure assessment: consumption data (e.g. national food consumption database, specific survey)

ab

63.

Q14b_fh_other

If 'other', can you precise ?

64.

Q30_own_DB

Question 30: Do you use an own database containing data for Risk Assessment?

[Modalité 1](#); [Modalité 2](#)

65.

Q16_DRDorS

Did you use a deterministic or stochastic model?

[Modalité 2](#); [Deterministic approach](#); [Other](#)

Une question "Si Autre, précisez" est associée à cette question.

67.

Q16a_DRa

Question 16a: Did you use a dose-response model ?

[Modalité 1](#); [Modalité 2](#)

68.

Q16b_DR

Question 16b: If 'yes', which one?

69.

Q17a_SA

Question 17a: Did you perform an evaluation such as a sensitivity or uncertainty analysis?

[Modalité 1](#); [Modalité 2](#)

70.

Q20a_publication

Question 20a: Is there any publication reference of the QMRA ?

[Modalité 1](#); [Modalité 2](#)

71.

Q22a_intervention

Question 22a: Did you recommend an intervention strategy?

[Modalité 1](#); [Modalité 2](#)

72.

Q25a_dataYS

Question 25a: Did you use any data produced by yourself?

[Modalité 1](#); [Modalité 2](#)

73.

Q26a_DataLite

Question 26a: Did you use data from literature?

[Modalité 1](#); [Modalité 2](#)

74.

Q27a_DataSN

Question 27a: Did you use data from a scientific network?

[Modalité 1](#); [Modalité 2](#)

75.

Q19_software

Which software was used?

Modalité 1; Modalité 2; MicroHibro; R; @Risk; FSSP; FSK-Lab; Matlab; Risk ranger; Swift QMRA; FDA-iRisk;
Other1

An "If Other, please specify" question is associated with this question. You can check more than one box.

ab

77.

Q20_output

What kind of output? be specific and give the dimension of the output: e.g. no. of cfu ingested per person per year, no. of cases per 100,000 persons per year

ab

78.

Q21b_pub

Publication reference of the QMRA (e.g. Permanent link to a website, doi, article)

ab

79.

Q22_mrsc

Did you indicate the main route or source of contamination?

ab

80.

Q23b_reco

Did you recommend an intervention strategy?

81.

Q24_decision

Nature of the decision taken by risk manager using QMRA?

Modalité 1; Modalité 2; Technical instruction; Communication plan; Monitoring plan; No decision; Don't know;

Other

An "If Other, please specify" question is associated with this question. You can check more than one box.

ab

83.

Q25b_rdec

Publication reference of the riks manager decision?

84. Q25a_Publication_reference parmi "Modalité 1"

84.

Q25a_Publication_reference

Question 24a: Publication reference of the riks manager decision?

Modalité 1; Modalité 2; Don't know

ab

85.

Q26b_datap

Did you use any data produced by yourself?

ab

86.

Q27b_DatalitW

Question 26b: If 'yes', which one?

ab

87.

Q28b_DataSNW

Did you use data from a scientific network (please indicate) ?

ab

88.

Q29a_HI

For hazard identification?(eg. data from outbreak investigations, data related to number of sporadic cases, characteristics of microorganisms throughout the food chain)

ab

89.

Q29b_HC

For hazard characterisation?(e.g. used parameters in dose-response model)

ab

90.

Q29c_EA

For exposure assessment?microbiological data (e.g. surveillance plan, industry own check results, contamination data (prevalence and concentration), parameters for microbiological and food handling processes: growth (curves), inactivation, cross-contamination, etc.)

ab

91.

Q29d_EAc

For exposure assessment: consumption data (e.g. national food consumption database, specific survey)

ab

92.

Q29_publicly_share

●

Question 29: Are you willing to publicly share those data in raw?

[Modalité 1](#); [Modalité 2](#)

100. Q26a_dataYS parmi "Modalité 1"

ab

93.

Q31_own_DB

●

Question 30: Do you use an own database containing data for Risk Assessment?

[Modalité 1](#); [Modalité 2](#)

100. Q26a_dataYS parmi "Modalité 1"

ab

94.

Q32_DBpub

●

Question 32: Are you willing to make this database publicly assessible?

[Modalité 1](#); [Modalité 2](#)

100. Q26a_dataYS parmi "Modalité 1"

ab

95.

Q17a_DRa

Question 16a: Did you use a dose-response model ?

[Modalité 1](#); [Modalité 2](#)

ab

96.

Q17b_DR

Question 16b: If 'yes', which one?

ab

97.

Q18a_SA

Question 17a: Did you perform an evaluation such as a sensitivity or uncertainty analysis?

Modalité 1; Modalité 2

98.

Q21a_publication

Question 20a: Is there any publication reference of the QMRA ?

Modalité 1; Modalité 2; Don't know

99.

Q23a_intervention

Question 22a: Did you recommend an intervention strategy?

Modalité 1; Modalité 2

100.

Q26a_dataYS

Question 25a: Did you use any data produced by yourself?

Modalité 1; Modalité 2

101.

Q27a_DataLite

Question 26a: Did you use data from literature?

Modalité 1; Modalité 2

102.

Q28a_DataSN

Question 27a: Did you use data from a scientific network?

Modalité 1; Modalité 2

103.

Q11_pop1

Question 11: Who is the target population of the study?

Infant 0 - 3 months; Infant 0 - 6 months; Infant 3 - 6 months; Infant 6 - 12 months; Children less than 4 years; Infant or toddler; Adult; Men; Pregnant or lactating women; Seniors; Teenagers; Women; Athletes; Bodybuilders; Menopausal women; Weight-reducers; Other

An "If Other, please specify" question is associated with this question. You can check more than one box.